

Academic Motivation and General Self-efficacy Amongst Public and Private College Students

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Abstract

Academic motivation is one of the branches within the educational psychology which explains the desire of a student in academics and its performance. Whereas self-efficacy is referred to the ability to achieve your goal at a particular situation. The aim of this study was to find a relation between the Academic Motivation and General self-efficacy in college going students. This study is based on a quantitative data to compare the academic motivation and self-efficacy of Public and Private college students (N=110) residing in Delhi/NCR region, of age 18 to 25 years, additionally the relation between self-efficacy and academic motivation was investigated. The data was collected using an adaptive version of Academic Motivation scale (AMS-C 28) College Version (Vallerand, 1989) for Academic Motivation and General Self-efficacy scale (Schwarzer, 1995) for the collection of self-efficacy data. AMS identifies three level of motivation in academics- Intrinsic, Extrinsic and Amotivation. The data for was collected from private university and for Public University. The results showed for the first hypothesis showed that the difference between the two mean is statistically significance ($t=-3.910$, $p<0.001$), this proves that there is a significant difference between the private and public student GSE scores. For the second hypothesis the mean score difference came out to be -28.490. which concludes that the private students had significantly higher academic motivation score than the public students. Hence, the hypothesis 2 is accepted. The third hypothesis showed that there is a positive correlation between both the variables and is significant at 0.01 level (two-tailed). It was also seen that Extrinsic motivation (Identified) is higher in both public and private university.

Keywords: *Academic Motivation, General-Efficacy, Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Amotivation, Public and Private University*

Introduction

Human desire is unlimited & to reach that goal an individual should have a positive driving force so that it makes them feel enthusiastic & optimistic, this is known as motivation. Behind every driving force is motivation which leads an individual to maintain & guide goal-oriented behaviour. When it comes to motivation it depends on the individual itself how they adhere to get motivated, in short it helps you to act in a way that moves closer to the desired goal. The concept of motivation not just pervades in our professional but in private life too. According to Kleninginna & Kleinginna (1981a), Motivation is specified as an internal state or behaviour that is activated by specific condition to give direction, aspiration or to vitalize & direct determined behaviour which is impact by the

need & desire on the intensity & direction of the behaviour. To this definition Franken (2006), provided a further part to the earlier definition by adding the arousal, direction, & the tenacity of behaviour.

Motivation

We define it as a process to reach intensity, persistence & direction towards the goal of an individual. In other words when an individual take action to achieve their need, goal & desire through emotional & psychological force is refer as motivation. Here intensity is referred to how hard a person tries to achieve the goal but to reach one should put a positive effort for the desired direction. The next step leads to the persistence, which means how long the individual takes to main that effort. Motivation

plays a very critical role in achievement in academics. Motion is referred as the desire & inclination to engage in an activity whereas Motivation is academics is referred by accomplishment in academic settings. It influences the level of effort, persistence, goal setting, interest & emotional wellbeing in a student.

Motivation in Academics

According to Mohamandi (2006), Within educational perceive, motivation is a multi-dimensional structure which is interrelated with learning & Motivation is academics. In the branch of educational psychology, the most upcoming topic is Motivation is academics. McClelland, et al. (1953) defined a student desire in academic subjects when competence is evaluated against a standard of performance or excellence. Motivation is academics is a vast term which include a large scale of terms like self-efficacy, resilience, determination etc. but all these come to a single conclusion which is motivation.

“In the discipline of education motivation is a tri-dimensional phenomena consisting of individual belief in ability in carrying out a specific task, reason & goals of the individual in doing the task & the emotional responses concerning carrying out the task” (Hassanzadeh & Amuee, 2001). Researchers’ have divided motivation into two major groups which are internal & external motivation. “While the individual influenced by the external motivation with an independent goal undertaken a specific activity, the internal motivation provides the sufficient incentive for doing a task.” (Mohamadi, 2006).

Pintrich (2003) stated that motivation is more important factor affecting the academics success or failure of an individual in the learning process. Many studies have stated that when it comes to knowledge & success, Motivation is academics is an important aspect for better performance. With increase in negative experience in school & college students begin to stop trying because they think it will make no difference & lead to lose of interest or dropouts.

Motivation is academics is related to psychological construct like Self-efficacy, Goal Orientation, Self- Awareness & Self- regulation. These factors interact with each other so that the individual feel motivated & leads to increase in academic performance. One of the most remarkable theories that explains about Motivation is academics is Self-Determination Theory by Deci & Ryan (1985), which explains that every individual inherent psychological need like autonomy, relatedness & competence, & when these needs interact with each other they augment intrinsic motivation & engage in activities related to the academic task.

Social factor also plays an important part in Motivation is academics. Students learn from their teacher, peer groups, from their family culture & environment & all these factors can impact their motivation level. For example, if a student receives regular feedback & praise from their teacher, they are highly to get more motivated to engage in their task.

Motivation is academics is agile & can vary from time to time. It can be influenced by variety of factors which include personal context, social context goal orientation, self-efficacy, value, interest, educators & parents. Understanding the complexity of Motivation is academics can help to improve the teaching & learning strategies to enhance the motivation of an individual for a better result.

Self-Efficacy

Albert Bandura termed self-efficacy, which simply indicates the ability of an individual to achieve the required goal. He proposed by concept by his own words, “How well one can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situation” (Bandura, 1977). Self-efficacy is the individual’s belief in their capacity to perform effectively & exercise control over their functioning & over events that affect their lives (Garrido, 2020). It shows how confident students are about executing a specific task to attain their valued goal, while Motivation is academics is based on a person desire to achieve (Ackerman, 2020).

The theory of Self-efficacy that was developed in 1977 by Bandura, proposed that self-efficacy influence individual motivation & their behaviour. The result showed that students with higher level of self-efficacy have positive impact on academic task. Whereas there will be a decrease in Motivation is academics is the general self-efficacy level is low.

Relation Between Motivation in Academics & Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy has a strong relation with motivation in academics. In educational setting when an individual self-efficacy is at a high level, they are most likely to be motivated & engage in more academic task to achieve better outcome.

A study was conducted by Johnsen et al. (2017) showing a positive relation between Motivation is academics & General self-efficacy among high school student. The findings shows that students who are motivated have higher self-efficacy, indicating that motivation plays a significant role in predicting self-efficacy beliefs.

Key factors between self-efficacy & Motivation are academics

Task engagement: There is likely to have more approach in academic task when there is a high level of self-efficacy. They engage in taking up more task & learning new things.

Achievement: Students with high self-efficacy set a challenging goal as they believe they can attain it. They are more likely to have higher achievement in academics & a great sense of responsibility.

Self-regulated learning: This is referred to the ability to set a goal, plan, monitor & to regulate one's own learning. This is completely tied by Motivation is academics.

Attribution for success & failure: Students with high level of self-efficacy are more successful than the student with low self-efficacy. It is accomplished by the student's own effort, interest, ability & strategies.

Emotion & Affective factor: It is said that students with high self-efficacy have

experienced positive emotion which enhance their motivation to engage in academic task.

The connection between Motivation is academics & self-efficacy is multifaced. The primary objective is to assess & differentiate the levels of Motivation in academics & General self-Efficacy among college going studying at Public & Private Colleges/Universities.

Method

The purpose of this present research is to examine relationship among Motivation is Academics & General Self-Efficacy of Public & Private University Student.

Research Design

For this study descriptive correlational research design & T-test was used. A quantitative research method for the collection & analysis of data. This research design helps to find a pattern & make prediction about the relation between the variables. Researches uses the quantitative method in a research work to identify the variables & avail the data collection. (Bhandari, 2020).

Descriptive Correlational Design is a type of design which is used in research studies that aims to establish a relation between variables (McBurney & White, 2009) & helps to give a picture of the situation where as a quantitative research method provides a description of two or more variables & their relation with each other. In this study, a parametric test known as the t-test was employed to compare the means of two groups, namely the Public and Private groups.

Hypothesis

For this study there are three hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Significant difference in Motivation is academics of Public & Private University/ College Students.

Hypothesis 2: Significant difference in General Self-Efficacy of Public & Private University/ College Students.

Hypothesis 3: Significant correlation between Motivation is Academics & General Self-efficacy of college going students.

Sample

A total number of 110 college going student from Delhi/NCR, India participated in this research. They were divided into two equal groups, first a Private University group with total number of 55 participants & the second groups consist of Public University with total of 55 participants.

The participants were selected by simple randomization sampling method, the main objective of this strategy was to make sure that the college students taking part are representative of population of interest therefore students of all gender were allowed to participate in the research. To be a part of this research a student should be of age 18 to 25, residing in Delhi/NCR region.

The collection of the data for the study was done using both offline & online method & were given the consent of voluntarily participated, those who agreed were allow to participate in this research. If by any chance they withdrawal from the study or had a incomplete questionnaire they were removed from the data.

The following data shows the sample in the given table below:

Table 1, Number of Participants

S. No.	Gender	No. of Participants	Percentage
1	Male	28	25.45
2	Female	82	74.55

Table 2, Qualification Details

S. No.	Qualification	No. of Participants	Percentage
1	Graduate	80	72.72
2	Postgraduate & More	30	27.27

Table 3, Age Groups of Participants

Age	Number of Participants
18-20	53
21-23	50
24-25	7

Procedure

For this research data was collected from Private University & Public University, the total number of participants were 110 college students who were divided into two equal groups. To know the required data in determining the influence of Motivation is academics & self-efficacy of the participant, information was gathered through offline survey (60%) by questionnaires & online survey (40%) through Google forms with participants consent. The survey was made up of thirty-eight questions, no time limit was given to the participants but would last maximum till 20 minutes. The questionnaire was divided into four parts: the first contains the consent form for the participation in the survey. The Second part consist of the demographic information of the participant (Name, age, course, year & type of university/college), they were informed that their identity will be anonyms & will only be used for research purposes. The thirst & fourth part contained the questionnaire of Motivation is academics Scale & the General Self-efficacy. Before the starting they were informed that if they don't feel well to continue the survey they can withdraw. For the online survey it was provided that they can ask any concern or clarification through the mail provided. The data analysis for this survey was performed using the statistical software SPSS & Excel. To analyse the data Pearson Corelation & T-test was used.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the approval was approved by the participants a consent form was made which they had to sign before participating in the survey. The ethical standards for this research were strictly observed. Prior to participating in the study, the applicants were clearly notified that their responses would be treated as confidential and would be utilized solely for research purposes while being overseen by experts.

Result

To access the first hypothesis i.e., there will be positive correlation between Motivation is academics & General Self-efficacy of college

going students. To assess these results Pearson product Moment Correlation Method was used.

Table 4 Correlation

S. No.	Variables	N	r(PC)	Sig.
1	Motivation in Academics	110	0.489**	Sig*
2	Self- Efficacy	110	1	Sig*

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The second hypothesis discusses the significance of General self-efficacy and Public and private Universities/Colleges. For this hypothesis, an Independent T-test was used, which shows a significant difference among General Self-efficacy and the two groups, i.e., Public and private Universities (Table 5 T-test for General Self-Efficacy).

This third hypothesis talks about the significance of Motivation in academics & in Public & Private University/Colleges. For this hypothesis, Independent T-test was used. This shows a significant difference in the Motivation in academics & two groups, i.e., Public & Private Universities (Table 6 T-test for Motivation in Academics).

Table 7 (Domains of Motivations in Academics) indicates the group stats of all the 7 domains in AMS, this helps us to know which domain is least & most responsive in both the groups i.e., Public University/College & Private University/ College. They are mainly to know the which type of motivation is higher among all the other domain.

Discussion

According to Lee et al. (2018), Motivation in academics can be defined as a multifaceted that includes different type of motivation, which commonly is known as Intrinsic Motivation i.e., engaging in activities for interest & enjoyment, Extrinsic Motivation i.e., to gain reward or to avoid punishment & Amotivation i.e., lack of motivation to engage in any activities. In 2019, Schwarzer & Jerusalem said that self-efficacy is a belief is the capacity of an individual to deploy

motivation, resources & action to meet the given demands. They state that self-efficacy is the force to influence individual’s behaviour & manage the demanding situation.

Vallerand, in 1998, conducted research on Motivation in academics & self-efficacy & revealed that there was a positive relation among these two variables & showed a significance difference even if there was no difference between the gender.

The aim was to discover a positive relation between Motivation, academics, and self-efficacy among college-going students. The demographic data shows that the majority of applicants were between the ages of 18 and 25, with 53 participants. For the age group 21 to 23, the total number of participants was 50, followed by 7 participants for 24 to 25.

The gender distribution for this present shows that the total number of males is 28 at 25.45%, & Females with a total 82 number of students at 74.55%. The qualification of the participants was divided into two groups with 72.72% for Bachelor students (80 college students) & 27.27% for Postgraduate or above (30 college students). All the participants are college-going students, and the main objective was to find a correlation between the two selected variables. The groups were divided into two equal participants of Public & Private university. The scales that were used for this research were AMS-C 28 & GSE.

As demonstrated in Table 4, it shows the correlation between the two variables. The total number of participants were 110 for both the variables. In Motivation in academics it shows that the Pearson correlation is Motivation in academics is exact 1 & self-efficacy is .489 (p<0.001) & same goes for Self-efficacy (p<0.001). This explains that there is a positive correlation between both the variables & is significant at 0.01 level (two-tailed). There are many researches that do agree with this result finding. A recent study conducted in 2021 by Tipon et.al. conducted research on Self-efficacy & its relationship with Motivation in academics on the high school students in Philippines. The result showed that there is a positive correlation

between the two variables with the alpha level of 0.01 level. Further, Kharameh in 2018 proved that the academic self-efficacy has a relation with students' Motivation is academics that is as self-efficacy increase motivation increases too.

In Table 5, shows the significance level ($p < 0.001$) at both one side p & two side p . for both Public & Private university GSE, the total number of participants are 55 in each group with the mean of 30.51 in Public & 33.78 in private. The significant difference of these two groups are 0.390 which is lesser than the 0.5 level. While looking at the group statistic, the mean private GSE score is higher than the public GSE scores, indicating private students have higher self-efficacy belief than public students. Even at the Levene's test for equality conducted on SPSS shows that there is a difference between the two means as both equal & unequal variance are present in the table. The t-test results shows that the difference between the two mean is statistically significance ($t = -3.910$, $df = 108$, $p < 0.001$). this proves the hypothesis 1 is accepted that there is a significant difference between the private & public student GSE scores.

In Table 6, the result shows the public group had the mean of 123.96 & a SD of 22.529, private mean score is 152.45 & SD of 17.902. The independent sample t-test shows that Leven's test is not significant ($p = 0.407$), indicating the assumption of equal variance. The t-test showed significant difference between the two groups in Motivation is academics score ($t = -7.343$, $df = 108$, $p < 0.001$, two tailed). The men score difference came out to be -28.490. which concludes, private students had significantly higher Motivation is academics score than the public students. Hence, hypothesis 2 is accepted.

According to Table 7, the mean is shown of all the 7 types of Motivation in academic domains on the scale of AMS-C. It was concluded that in public universities, the least required motivation is AMO, which signifies Amotivation with a mean value of 10.67 & the highest required motivation is iden, which is denoted as Extrinsic motivation- Identified with a mean value of

21.27. For Private motivation, the least motivation is also Amotivation, with a mean value of 15.62 & the highest motivation is the same as Public, which is Extrinsic Motivation to identified.

Present study results show a correlation among the 2 variables & significant difference between the two groups. Furthermore, there are quite a few studies to prove the given result. Some studies also conclude that self-efficacy & motivation may lead to better achievement in academics of an individual.

Limitation

This present study did experience some limitation. The first was that the survey was collected from the same demographic area, even though the result have shown a positive result there maybe variance if had a large sample size of this research.

As the sample size was very small with a specified demographic location leads to second restriction, future researches can work with enlarged sample size by including other students & universities.

Third limitation shows that the gender distribution is unequal at extreme level & may impact the research.

Conclusion

Despite the limitation the findings of the study show a positive & first step towards the identification between the relation among Motivation is academics & self-efficacy. Objective of this present study was proved correct that there is a positive relation between the variables & a significance between the groups.

Beside this it was also shown that there is a significant difference between Private & Public University even though the demographic was same. The Private University have higher Motivation is academics as well as higher self-efficacy in comparison to Public University, & was concluded that amotivation is least & external motivation is higher in both groups.

Group Statistics						
	Students	N	Mean	Sig.	Significance	
					One-Side p	Two-Side p
GSE	0	55	30.51	0.390	<.001	<.001
	1	55	33.78		<.001	<.001

*Table 5: T-Test for General Self-efficacy

Group Statistics						
	Students	N	Mean	Sig.	Significance	
					One-Side p	Two-Side p
AMS	0	55	123.96	0.407	<.001	<.001
	1	55	152.45		<.001	<.001

*Table 6: T-Test for Motivation is academics

Group Statistics							
	Students	N	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
know	0	55	6	28	19.89	5.123	0.691
	1	55			23.80	3.234	0.436
acc	0	55	4	28	18.18	4.468	0.603
	1	55			21.53	3.948	0.532
stim	0	55	5	28	16.09	5.075	0.684
	1	55			20.71	4.791	0.646
iden	0	55	4	28	21.27	5.057	0.682
	1	55			24.89	3.004	0.405
intro	0	55	4	28	16.62	5.955	0.803
	1	55			21.45	4.951	0.668
reg	0	55	6	28	21.24	6.200	0.836
	1	55			24.45	3.442	0.464
amo	0	55	4	28	10.67	6.019	0.812
	1	55			15.62	4.680	0.631

*Table 7: Domains of Motivation in academics

References

Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioural Change. *Psychological Review*, 84 (2), 191-215.

Bhandari, K. (2020). Quantitative research method. *Journal of Medical Society*, 34(2), 112-117.

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York, NY: Plenum Press.

Del, J.R.B., & Napawit, J. (2018). Student’s self-efficacy and motivation on their academic performance in using English language. *St. Theresa Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4.

Franken, R. (2006). *Human Motivation* (6th ed.) Florence, KY: Wadsworth.

- Hassanzadeh, R., & Amuee, N. (2001). The relation between academic motivation and academic achievement students. *Social and behavioural science*, 15, 399-402.
- Lee, J., et al. (2018). Academic motivation and self-efficacy as predictors of college students' academic performance. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 90, 90-99.
- Lee, W., et al. (2018). Academic motivation and self-efficacy as predictors of college students' academic performance. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 8(2), 35-46.
- McBurney, D. & White, T. (2009). *Research Methods*. New York, NY: Cengage Learning.
- McClelland, et al. (1953). Academic Motivation: For the love of loving. *Research on program development and assessment methodologies*, 35.
- Mohammadi, Y. (2006). *Educational Psychology: theory and practice*.
- Mohamadi, Y. (2006). *Understanding motivation and emotion*. Reev JM, 4th Edn.
- Pintrich, P.R. (2003). A motivational science perspective on the role of student motivation in learning and teaching contexts. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(4), 667.
- Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). Generalized self-efficacy scale. In J. Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston (Eds.), *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs* (pp. 35-37). Windsor, UK: NFER-NELSON.
- Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (2019). Generalized Self-Efficacy scale. In J. A. Sinclair, M. R. Smith, & L. M. Tetrick (Eds.) *Handbook of organizational measurement* (pp. 234-237). New York: Routledge.
- scTipon, F., et al. (2021), The self-efficacy and its relation on academic motivation to the senior high school students from public school amidst the new normal education in the Philippines. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative ideas in Education*, 7(3), 2935-2947.
- Vallerand, R.J. et. al. (1993). Academic motivation scale (ams-c 28) college (cegep) version. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 52(53), 1992-1993.